

Rendering tiny tactile signals through a miniaturized, self-contained hydraulic haptic thimble

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Abstract—The role of tiny tactile signals such as contact transients and vibrations is very informative in fine manipulation. Yet, these signals are challenging to be rendered with wearable haptic devices, both in virtual reality and in tele-manipulation setups. Low noise and wide bandwidth rendering has to be achieved by the actuating mechanism, hence here the conventional micro-gearred motors are not a suitable solution. On the other hand, direct drive electromagnetic actuators, such as voice-coil, result in more cumbersome device due to the lack of a reduction mechanism. We propose a miniature hydraulic actuator based on a linear electromagnetic motor with an embedded ferrofluidic sealing. Remarkably it shows no static friction due to the magneto-hydrodynamic levitation effect of the ferrofluid, and the output force can be scaled, by varying the radius of the actuator, without introducing noise and friction. We characterize here a prototype of the actuator, evidencing the linearity and friction-less output behavior, and we present as a concept design a compact and soft haptic thimble integrating the proposed actuator.

Index Terms—haptic feedback, tactile, wearable, hydraulic, ferrofluid

I. INTRODUCTION

Typical miniature electromagnetic motors implemented in wearable haptic devices are coupled with micro-sized gear reduction, in order to amplify the output force in a reduced mass [1], [2], yet at the cost of a very limited output bandwidth, or of introduction of noise in the rendering (due to gears vibrations). However, importance of high-frequency components in sense of touch is evidenced by the high sensitivity of fingerpads mechanoreceptors to fast dynamic signals [3]. Perception of such high frequency haptic signals becomes very informative during virtual exploration ([4]) and tele-manipulation ([5]). On the other hand, direct-drive electromagnetic motors and voice coils allow for high quality haptic rendering, ranging from constant to high frequency force components, with the drawback of a limited maximum output force [6] or a relatively heavy device [7].

Regarding noise and quality of the signals, ergonomics of the interface between the actuator and the skin tissues plays also a critical role: air gaps, static friction and backlash in

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Fig. 1. Prototype of the haptic thimble making use of the direct-drive hydraulic actuator

Fig. 2. Scheme of the operation principle: the ferrofluid acts both as a frictionless hydraulic sealing and as a polar expansion for the electro-magnetic linear actuator

the transmission impact the rendering of informative signal components. To this regard pneumatic or hydraulic actuators with soft interfaces between the actuated part and the fingerpad have been proposed for haptic rendering, such as in [8], [9]. The main disadvantage is that conventional pneumatic actuators need cumbersome actuating units, that are usually placed remotely and tethered to the wearable interface.

II. METHODS

We investigated whether more compact, direct-drive hydraulic actuators could be designed for embedded, untethered wearable haptic devices. The main problem in miniaturizing fluidic actuators is the sealing, which usually introduce significant friction in the mechanism. In [10] a miniaturized pump mechanism was developed using ferrofluid as a sealing cushion between a cylinder and a moving magnet: since the cushion is liquid, it exhibits no static friction. In this work we applied the method for developing a direct-drive, miniaturized hydraulic actuator for haptic rendering (scheme of the working principle is shown in Figure 2). We propose a first application of the actuator in a self-contained, hydraulic haptic thimble. A prototype of the thimble has been implemented and characterized. Mass of the actuator was 3.2 g, with 4 mm internal diameter of the cylinder (extended details are presented in [11]). Then, a prototype of the thimble has been built in 3D stereolithography (SLA) using soft resins. The thimble could be prototyped in one piece including the soft membrane interface, and excluding the hydraulic actuator. Total mass of the final device was 7.8 g. For characterization, the actuator was coupled with a pressure sensor (MPXH6115AC6U) and driven by a high frequency modulation PWM driver (TI DRV8835 at 200 Khz modulation) at 3.7 V.

III. RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

Characterization of the actuator at the bench clearly shows the interesting features of the ferrofluidic-based sealing. In particular the substantial absence of static friction is magnified in Figure 3: a flowing current intensity in the order of a few milli-amperes is already able to increase the output pressure. Peak output pressure was equal to 112 mbar. Bandwidth of the device was also measured (Figure 4), showing a cutoff frequency at 200 Hz, which is useful for rendering wide bandwidth, dynamic haptic signals.

To conclude, we have propose a novel self-enclosed hydraulic haptic thimble, which benefits from adaptability of the soft interface, and quality of the output signals due to the direct-drive pressure modulation with no significant static friction. In addition, the hydraulic interface allows for easy scaling of the output force without mechanical reducers, hence without introducing noise in the rendering. Further investigation will investigate application of the device for rendering tiny transients in tele-manipulation experimental setup, and in virtual manipulation with informative feedback for neuro-rehabilitation purposes.

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Fig. 3. Current to pressure characteristic (left) and detail of the same experiment at very low current, evidencing the substantial absence of static friction (right).

Fig. 4. Frequency response of the actuator connected to an analog pressure sensor.

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